

Effects of Diet Formulation on the Yield, Proximate Composition and Fatty Acid Profile of the Black Soldier Fly (*Hermetia illucens* L.) Prepupae Intended for Animal Feed.

Pier Paolo Danieli¹, Carola Lusiana², Laura Gasco², Andrea Amici, Bruno Ronchi¹

¹ Department of Agriculture and Forest Sciences; University of Tuscia, Viterbo, Italy; amici@unitus.it; ronchi@unitus.it

² Department of Agricultural Forest and Food Sciences; University of Torino, Grugliasco (TO), Italy; carola.lussiana@unito.it; laura.gasco@unito.it

* Correspondence: danieli@unitus.it; Tel.: +39-0761-357349

Table S1. Effect of decolorization treatment with potassium permanganate (KMnO₄) on the weight loss of three different samples of black soldier fly prepupae (BSFP) meal submitted to the demineralization/deproteinization procedure described by Liu et al. [36].

Sample	Total initial weight ¹ (g)	Total post demineralization/deproteinization treatment weight (g)	Total post-decolorization treatment weight (g)
#1	0.095	0.046	0.046
#2	0.094	0.045	0.045
#3	0.099	0.049	0.049
Average	0.096	0.047	0.047

¹ Total weight includes the weight of the ANKOM modified bag and the weight of BSFP meal.